

Evaluation of Proximal Contact Points in Fixed Prosthesis

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ABSTRACT

KEY WORDS:

Contact points.,
Metal Crowns,
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A cross-sectional study was done to clinically assesses the tightness of proximal contact points of fixed dental prosthesis with natural teeth. Ninety (90) patients visiting the Department of Prosthodontics, Rajarajeshwari dental college Bangalore were taken into consideration for the study. The crowns as a single unit were prepared and fabricated at the same institute were included. A total of 180 Proximal Contact Points were assessed with the dental floss and categorized as acceptable, open and tight. Among these, 129 were acceptable, 39 Open and 12 were tight. Out of 180 Proximal Contact Points, 60 were Porcelain Fused to Metal (PFM) 60 were all metal, and 60 were zirconia crowns. The crowns were fabricated and cemented. The Proximal Contact Points of adjacent natural dentition in same patient may serve as guide for assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Root canal treated teeth are restored using fixed dental prostheses which protect remaining tooth structure and may also act as retainer of Fixed Partial Denture (FPD) for replacement of missing tooth. They may also be responsible for maintaining occlusion, function and provide esthetics¹. Proximal Contact Points of a tooth or restoration remain in close association, connection or in touch with an adjacent tooth in the same arch². Weak or slightly opened Proximal Contact Points may cause food impaction, dental caries, periodontal disease, failure of occlusion and an undesirable drift of the teeth. On the other hand, too tight contact may damage the periodontal tissue or cause improper tooth movement or interfere with the physiological placement of the teeth³.

When new prosthesis is fabricated, the Proximal Contact Points has to be checked during try in stage on the cast and intra oral before final cementation⁴. The strength of Contact Point is generally determined by dentist clinically with the dental floss that passes through the CP with a snap. The objective of this study was to assess the Proximal Contact Points of fixed prostheses with natural teeth clinically.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Prosthodontics, Rajarajeshwari dental college Bangalore. Ninety (90) patients visiting the department for receiving crowns in maxillary or mandibular, premolar or distal were included after informed consent. The crowns, as a single unit abutment prepared and fabricated in the same institute by postgraduate students were included. Porcelain fused to metal (PFM), all metal crowns, and Zirconia Crowns were accepted. Crowns with no adjacent natural tooth, active periodontal disease, generalized spacing were excluded. Clinical assessment of Proximal Contact Points was done by the postgraduate Students. The dental floss was wrapped around the index fingers of both hands and floss was passed through the Proximal Contact Points under assessment. Proximal Contact Points was categorized as acceptable, open, and tight. Acceptable, if dental floss could be passed with little resistance or as much resistance as in natural dentition on other side. Open Proximal Contact Points were those which allowed the dental floss to pass without resistance. If dental floss shredded or could not pass at all, it was categorized as tight. The variables including age, gender, tightness of Proximal Contact Points, crowns as a single unit of FPD, material of prostheses were collected on a structured proforma. The means and percentages were calculated using SPSS 22.

A total of 90 patients were included with mean age of 35 ± 6 years. Among these, 38 (55.1%) were males and 31 (44.1%) females. A total of 180 Proximal Contact Points were assessed, among these, 129 were found acceptable, 39 Open and 12 tight. Single crown Out of a total 180 Proximal Contact Points, 60 were Porcelain Fused to Metal (PFM) 60 were all metal and 60 were zirconia crowns. Out of 60 Proximal Contact Points of zirconia crowns 51 were acceptable, 2 were open contact and 7 were tight contact, out of 60 Proximal Contact Points of Metal ceramic crowns 38 were acceptable, 18 were open contact and 4 were tight contact, out of 60 Proximal Contact Points of Metal crowns 40 were acceptable, 15 were open contact and 5 were tight contact.

The term Proximal Contact Points refers to the area of proximal contour height on the mesial or distal surface of a tooth that touches its adjacent tooth in the same arch⁵. Different methods

have been suggested to check the Proximal Contact Points before the cementation. The dentists assess the strength of proper Proximal Contact Points in clinical treatment by passing a floss with a snap. This method is simple but it is difficult to detect the detailed changes in the strength⁶. Dorfer *et al.* measured Proximal Contact Points strength with a calibrated metal strip (0.05 mm thick), and reported that the strength varied between teeth, arches and function⁷. We carried out clinical assessment manually with the floss as it was practical and gave the fair idea of the tightness of Proximal Contact Points.

Data obtained from this study showed discrepancies in Proximal Contact Points of crowns. Discrepancies in Proximal Contact Points and anatomic contour of the crowns may have adverse effects on surrounding tissues⁸. Discrepancies in Proximal Contact Points were observed in the form of tight and open Proximal Contact Points. One reason of tight contact points may be due to over contoured crown on proximal surfaces. It also reduces embrasure space which results in broadening of the Col area, causing pressure and irritation on the papilla. Over-contoured crown decreases gingival embrasure leading to gingival inflammation and inhibit effective oral hygiene; therefore, the axial reduction of tooth structure should follow the original contour of the tooth so that final restoration is closer to the natural anatomy of that tooth⁹. Frequently, dentists prepare the axial surfaces to be flat, forcing technicians to make over contoured crown with wide occlusal tables. Many a times it may not be possible for even good technicians to overcome the discrepancies of preparation.

Tight contact points make the interdental area to floss extremely difficult for patients. It also makes the area highly susceptible for caries. Proximal Contact Points within normal limits were associated with a lesser number of carious lesions in adjacent natural teeth. Tight Proximal Contact Points had greater association with presence of caries in adjacent natural teeth than open contact. Presence of carious lesion was observed less in teeth adjacent to crown with open than those with tight Proximal Contact Points. Greater discrepancies in Proximal Contact Points between crown and distal teeth were observed than that between a crown and mesial tooth, however, in this study we did not assess the mesial and distal contact points separately and did not compare them with each other.

Wessell *et al.* suggest that open Proximal Contact Points occur less frequently as compared to tight. However, this study showed contradictory result to Wessell *et al.* study and suggested Open Proximal Contact Points to be higher than the tight Proximal Contact Points.

The crown should be evaluated both clinically and radiographically before final cementation.

CONCLUSION

It is, therefore, recommended on the basis of results of this study and following discussion that the ideal proximal contact points are imperative for the success of fixed prostheses and these must be checked for excessive looseness and tightness. From the study it can be concluded that proximal contact point is better in zirconia single crown. The proximal contact point in metal crown is not as good as zirconia crown but better than metal ceramic crown. Acceptability of proximal contact points may be optimized by following standardized procedures during fabrication and vigilant check up by dentist before cementation. If any doubt exists, prosthesis may be cemented temporarily and checked for food impaction in few days' times before permanent cementation. The proximal contact points of natural dentition in the same patient may be good guide for assessment.

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